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ANNOTATION

In this article, intertextuality is one of the complex features of the text, it appears in various forms and performs various functions. This category has been widely studied in relation to the functions it serves in literary texts. However, its explicit, direct application can be seen in more scientific texts. In scientific discourse, intertextuality is the most important and universal means of shaping the content of a text. Thus, the quotation and reference form a micrometer within a general macrometer, noting that a scientific work is somehow related to other studies. This ensures the scientific development of science, the commercial development of knowledge, the formation of consistency and heredity in accordance with traditions (Chernyavskaya 2005: 49). Analysis of the cases mentioned in the article encourages us to recognize that intertextuality is not only the main feature of scientific discourse, but also an important tool for its formation.

Key words: information content, segmentation, cohesion, modality, coherence, intentionality, addressee, situationality, intertextuality, allusion, explicit, quotation, communicative.

A scientific text, like any linguistic structure, differs from other speech structures based on a specific set of categorical symbols. Linguists have proposed different classifications of these categories. In particular, I.R. Galperin lists such categories as informativeness, segmentation, coherence, continuity, modality, integrity, completeness (Galperin 1981). German researchers W. Dressler and R.A. Beaugrand notes that this classification is associated with the status of the text, including: 1) coherence, which ensures the mutual connection of parts; 2) logical-semantic connection of text fragments - coherence; 3) the connection of structural and spiritual integrity with the communicative goal - intentionality; 4) targeting – taking into account the position and mental state of the recipient when transmitting information; 5) information content - the level of importance or ease of information; 6) situational – correspondence of the form and content of the text to the conditions of communication; 7) intertextuality includes the reconstruction of a previously known meaning in a text (Bogrand, Dressler 1987; Boymirzaeva 2009: 58-59).

Attempts to create a classification of text categories continue. The results of research in this direction are certainly related to taking into account their structural and semantic differences. Additionally, some scholars prefer to divide text categories into required and elective activities. For example, D. Ashurova and I. Galieva include the signs of informativeness, modality, coherence, connectedness and intentionality to the group of categories that must be mandatory, i.e. must be present in any text, and note that the categories of intertextuality, implicitness, emotionality, and evaluation are not mandatory (Ashurova, Galieva 2016: 81).

Although intertextuality is included by the authors as an optional category, this category is typical for all types of texts. Scientific texts are no exception.

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According to M. Yuldashev, who analyzed the factors that ensure the manifestation of the phenomenon of intertextuality in artistic texts, “the presence in a certain artistic text of elements associated with other texts is the intertextuality of this text” (Yuldashev 2009). Other researchers also note that one text is associated with others using linguistic means of a certain kind. But the bulk of the work done is related to art, and this phenomenon has been little studied in the section of scientific texts (see: Chernyavskaya 2009).

Intertextuality is one of the important features of a scientific text, since scientific thinking is based on certain sources and the concept is activated in them. Any scientific phenomenon is forced to resort to various means of proof to prove the hypotheses and ideas it puts forward. The author, looking for ways to explain his opinion, studies the work of other scientists and hints at their conclusions. As a result of analyzing the opinions expressed by other researchers, confidence in one’s conclusion is created and the need to study the problem under discussion is justified. As a result, the participation in the text of modal units that express attitudes towards the opinions of other authors is activated.

It is difficult to imagine that any text will appear on its own in some space; it will certainly be created in some way and in connection with previous texts. Ideas expressed and written down in advance allow new linguistic structures to form and acquire social status. Vocabulary items, phrases, patterns of syntactic devices, emotional devices that are in motion in a language have all been used at some point by other speakers and authors. However, the degree of their activation and location in each text is different, giving each text individuality and showing its similarities and dissimilarities with others. In general, a text without intertextual connections is difficult to understand.

With a narrow interpretation of intertextual connection, thematic connections are taken into account, that is, the author unites texts around a single theme using certain formal means. Intertextuality is openly and explicitly expressed when quotes, allusions, etc. are used in the text.

In interpreting this phenomenon in a broad sense, it is necessary to rely on the tradition of accepting each text as a universal or global text. The theory of globality was first developed by M.M. It was formed in the work of Bakhtin (Bakhtin 1979), later by Y. Kristeva, Yu.M. Lotman, I.V. Arnold, E.V. Chernyavskaya was also supported by others. The content of the proposal to give the text a global character is to recognize the existence of a field of intersections between different “foreign” texts, reflecting a logical connection that generalizes the experience of individual people.

Thus, intertextuality in its narrow and broad interpretation is equally interpreted as a source of the formation of new content. N.V., who specifically studied the features of the manifestation of this category in a scientific text. Koroleva notes that this phenomenon can be studied in the context of a single discourse or within a series of discourses that are thematically similar (Koroleva 2004: 820).

French scientists (R. Barthes, J. Derrida) advocate a description of intertextuality in relation to the “text-cultural world” chain. R. According to Barth, the effect of linguistic activity is determined not by some “object-information”, but by “retelling” (Barth 1989). The linguocultural description of intertextuality in this regard is distinguished by its semantic description. In the semantic interpretation, intertextuality is considered as the ability to shape the content of a text by referring to the content of others, and in the linguocultural approach this category approaches the concept of cultural tradition (Lotman 1996: 14; Kuzmina 2009: 26).

Experts distinguish two main types of intertext links: citation and link. When using a quotation, which is a means of intertextual communication, a fragment taken from a specific source text takes place in the generated text. The author, citing the works of other scientists, tries to find the most convenient way to express his opinion. Brief quotations often use words and phrases that have evaluative meaning. Compare:

In contrast. EMR must either be limited to "relatively common" elements or be used with a wavelength spectrometer... Even then, the sensitivity of the PMP cannot approach 1 ppm (Legge G. Microprobe Analysis..., 1989:496);

These opinions about a concept or fragments of it cannot imply that the concept itself differs in different situations. A possible answer is that concepts are used only in thought and action; Such differentiated "opinions" or "fragments" in terms of intellectual and social process practically do not exist (Shi Hu. Discourse and Culture, 2013: 227).

One of the most common forms of intertextuality is the term citation, which serves to condense information by citing the authority of a referenced expert in a given field. For example, in the literature on linguistics V. Ergon and Humboldt's energy, the language of F. Saussure, V. "Sema" Skalichka, S. Trubetskoy's terms such as "distinctive sign" are used as a quote. Quotes of this type are found in other areas of science.

This is not just a list of properties; it is an integrated scheme supported by elementary figurative schemes such as "container" and "path", power dynamics, etc. (Fauconnier G. Mapping in Thought and Language, 1997: 19);

This is a typical feature of classical "chaotic systems". There are also regular "eigenfunctions" whose amplitude is concentrated along the short or long diagonal of the polygon (International Conference on Dynamical Systems and Chaos, 1994: 234);

In conclusion, the high-quality Ginda data presented here showed that time dependence.... (Astrophysical Journal, 1993. Volume 404. - P. 122);

However, the most common type of citation is the full citation of expert opinion. Compare:

The semantic concept of culture also corresponds to Geert's (1973:5) understanding when he tells us: "The concept of culture that I am expounding [...] is essentially semiotic. Believing with Max Weber that man is an animal suspended in a web of meaning that he himself has woven. I view culture as this network, and therefore its analysis is not an experimental science in search of law, but an interpretive science in search of meaning (Shi Xu. Discourse and Culture, 2013: 17);"

Ford and Fox (1996) note that a speaker's choice between forms such as "he" and "today" does not depend solely on the speaker's assessment of the listener's current cognitive awareness of the referent, but also has to do with "the continuation or shift of perception, e.g. attracting the attention of an uninvolved recipient or acknowledging the attention of a participant" (Laury R. Definiteness, 2014:58).

As noted by N.A. Kuzmina, quoting increases the value of the text by condensing information and "provides multi-layered content" (Kuzmina 2009: 120). This task requires a combination of object and subject planes of expression.

It is clear that the category of intertextuality performs various tasks in a scientific text. The dissertation of E. V. Mikhailova lists the referential, evaluative, etiquette and decorative tasks of this category (Mikhailova 1999: 58).

A link is a direct function of a quotation because the author refers to another text to convey additional information to the reader. Compare:

The fact that proper names imply that both the speaker and the addressee have some degree of knowledge of the referent (in Downing's terminology, proper names are "cognitive") "makes them particularly useful in contexts where the speaker wishes to demonstrate his authority to express an opinion to a particular respondent, as this often occurs in the context of disagreement" (Downing 1996: 136) (Lanry R. Defineteness, 2014:58).

There are different types of syllogisms, each of which has a name given by the scholastics... There are some conclusions that can be drawn from one premise.

From "some men are mortal" we can infer that "some mortals are men." According to Aristotle, this can also be deduced from "all men are mortal" (B. A. Russell, History of Western Philosophy, 1975:77).

The task of evaluation is manifested in the author's attitude to the given quotation. Commenting on the views of other authors is a special form of scientific dialogue and discussion. This task manifests itself in two contexts: with a negative assessment, it takes a critical form, and with a positive content, the author supports the previously expressed opinion and conclusion.

Other competent observers should repeat the experiments of M. Pasteur, and each result should be subjected to strict criticism. This is not disdain for M. Pasteur, it is only worthy of his genius and his skill (Nature, 1986. No. 33:2);

The idea of quaternion calculus, or that part of which was truly original and due to the genius of Hamilton alone, is undoubtedly beyond what can now be considered elementary mathematics (Priroda, 1986. No. 33: 543);

It is impossible that we should now begin to apply this theory to plant diseases, which were therefore mysterious and incurable (Microbiology. Historical contribution..... 1980: 115);

The Chinese concept of "he" allows for internal differences and even opposition, and is therefore best understood as the value of unity and diversity, and balancing contradictions. So, from this historical and cross-cultural perspective, the modern Chinese "concept should be translated as" "balanced harmony" and "equilibrium" (but see Chen, 2001) (Shi Xu. Discourse and Culture, 2013: 308).

Fulfilling the scientific task of a quotation is a symbol of respect for a particular scientific school, its representatives, and high appreciation of the works they created. Also, quotes and references are aimed at performing the function of decoration (scenery), designed to soften the style of the narrative.

Thus, intertextuality is one of the complex features of the text, which manifests itself in different forms and performs different tasks. The functions of this category in literary texts have been widely studied. But its obvious, direct use is observed more in the example of scientific texts. In scientific discourse, intertextuality is the most important and universal means of shaping the content of a text. Therefore, citation and reference form a microtext within the overall macrotex, indicating that the scientific work is somehow related to other studies. In this regard, the formation of scientific innovations, the economic development of knowledge, consistency and compliance with inherited traditions are ensured (Chernyavskaya 2005: 49).

Analysis of the above-mentioned cases encourages us to recognize that intertextuality is not only a fundamental feature of scientific discourse, but also an important means of shaping it.

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